

Thai Halal Products Brand Tips

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Abstract—The purpose of this research is to analyze the marketing strategies of Thai Halal products which related to the way of life for Thai Muslims. The expected benefit is the marketing strategy for brand building process for Halal products in Thailand. 4 elements of marketing strategies which necessary for the brand identity creation is the research framework: consists of Attributes, Benefits, Values and Personality. The research methodology was applied using qualitative and quantitative; 19 marketing experts with dynamic roles in Thai consumer products were interviewed. In addition, a field survey of 122 Thai Muslims selected from 175 Muslim communities in Bangkok was studied. Data analysis will be according to 5 categories of Thai Halal product: 1) Meat 2) Vegetable and Fruits 3) Instant foods and Garnishing ingredient 4) Beverages, Desserts and Snacks 5) Hygienic daily products; such as soap, shampoo and body lotion.

The results will explain some suitable representation in the marketing strategies of Thai Halal products as are: 1) Benefit; the characteristics of the product with its benefit. Consumers will purchase this product with the reason of; it is beneficial nutrients product, there are no toxic or chemical residues. Fresh and clean materials 2) Attribute; the exterior images that attract to consumer. Consumers will purchase this product with the reason of; there is a standard proof mark, food and drug secure proof mark and Halal products mark. Packaging and its materials should be draw attention. Use an attractive graphic. Use outstanding images of product, material or ingredients. 3) Value; the value of products that affect to consumers perception; it is healthy products. Accumulate quality of life. It is a product of expertise, manufacturing of research result. Consumers are important. It's sincere, honest and reliable to all. 4) Personality; reflection of consumers thought. The Personality feedback to them after they were consumes this product; they are health care persons. They are the rational person, moral person, justice person and thoughtful person like a progressive thinking.

Keywords—Marketing strategies, Product identity, Branding, Thai Halal products.

I. INTRODUCTION

ISLAM was established as a minority faith in Thailand with an estimated 10 million believers [1]. Popular opinion seems to hold that a vast Muslim minority is found in the three southern provinces of Thailand. However, research from the Thai Ministry of Foreign Affairs indicates that only 18% of Thai Muslims live in those three provinces. The rest are scattered throughout the country, with the largest concentrations being in Bangkok.

The pillars of the Islamic religion are Iman (faith), Ibadat (practice) and Ishan (ethics).

Iman (faith) consists of six articles of belief; belief in God (Allah); belief in all the prophets (nabi) and messengers (rusul); belief in the angels (mala'ika); belief in the Quran and the

holy books (kutub); belief in the day of judgement (qiyama) and in the resurrection (life after death); and belief in destiny (quadar).

Ibadat (practices) consist of five pillars of Islam, the term given to the five duties incumbent upon every Muslim. These duties are Shahada (profession of faith), Salah (prayers), Zakah (giving of alms), Sawm (fasting during Ramadan) and Haji (pilgrimage to Mecca).

Furthermore every Muslim must follow the ethic (Ishan). One of Ishan is Halal; the laws regarding which foods can and cannot be eaten and also on the proper method of slaughtering an animal for consumption. All Muslims have to observe the Halal. A variety of substances are considered as harmful (haram) for humans to consume and forbidden according to Qur'anic verses: pork (Qu'ran 2:173), blood (Qu'ran 2:173): all carnivorous and birds of prey, alcohol and other intoxicants (Qu'ran 5:90), food over which Allah's name is not pronounced (Qu'ran 6:121) etc. Halal and Haram are universal terms that apply to all facets of life. They are especially related to food products, food ingredients and food contact materials and cosmetics and products of personal care [2]; as on Table I.

TABLE I
THE CATEGORY OF THAI HALAL

Category of Halal	Category of Consumer Products
Edible Products	Meat
	Vegetable and Fruits
	Instant Products and Garnishing ingredient
	Beverages, Desserts and Snacks
Inedible Products	Hygienic Daily Products
Services	Hotel, Spa and Restaurant
	Banking and Logistic

In Thailand, Halal products are presented to the public with packaging of a general character. Halal products are represented with a Halal mark but without any Muslim characters such as brand name, visual, graphic and symbolic, Islamic mood and tone. Furthermore, there is not any advertisement for Thai Halal products. One of the causes is; Islam is a minority faith in Thailand with an estimated 10 million believers. Many of Thai Muslims cook their Halal food themselves or purchase local Halal products which non Islamic sign package from the Muslim community. However most of Thai Muslims purchase by seeking the Halal mark by only trust in their seller. It is for these reasons that Halal advertising seems to be unnecessary and not worth the investment.

In the present, Thai consumers are more complicated. There is a wide gap in age, gender, occupation, social class, lifestyle, culture and religion. The lifestyles of Thai Muslim consumers

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can be categorized into 9 groups [3]: 1) Modern life group 2) Information exposure group 3) Religious group 4) Self concern and social care group 5) Sporty and challenge group 6) Cyber and friend group 7) High vision and brand name group 8) Home sweet home group 9) Enjoy life and open minded group. These different lifestyles are encouragement to propaganda Thai Halal products. This is an opportunity to setup a niche market for Thai Muslim consumer, and respond to their emotional needs.

Creative execution refers to the manner in which an advertising appeal was carried out or presented. It is a way to present advertisement messages and stimulates consumer appeal. Creative executions are executed from the standpoint of both art and text. They are delivering the big idea in both verbal and non verbal forms of communication. Some of commonly creative execution techniques are [4]; 1) Use straight-sell or factual message 2) Use scientific or technical evidence 3) Demonstration 4) Comparison 5) Testimonials 6) Use a story as a slice of life 7) Animation 8) Personality symbol 9) Fantasy visual 10) Dramatization 11) Humor 12) Combinations of all.

The marketing strategy consist of 4 essential elements for brand building process that focus on different aspects of the product [5]; 1) Benefit; the characteristics of the product with its benefit such as taste, smell and texture or other function, production process, story of the manufacturer, production standard and trust, non chemical residues. 2) Attribute; the exterior images that attract to consumer such as brand name, characters of text, logos, colors, image of packaging, an advertising, public relations, image of retailer and shop, the QR code, barcode or industry standard code, standard proof mark, food and drug secure proof mark and Halal products mark. 3) Value; the value of products that affect to consumers perception such as valuable, reliable, concern to environment and community, originality, legends, the exquisite luxury. 4) Personality; reflection of consumers thought. The Personality feedback to them after they were consumes the product, such as modern look, teenager look, progressive thinking, futurism look, urbanism look, multi cultures lover, sport man or girl, extreme activity generation.

“A brand is a name, team, sign, symbol or design or a combination of them, which is intended to identify the goods or services of one seller or group of sellers and differentiate them from those of competitors

A brand can deliver up to four levels of meaning: attributes, benefits, values, personality. If a company treats a brand only as a name, it misses the point of branding” [6]

Creative branding is a way to setting corporate identity. Cause to sustainable the products, services and value added. Strong organization could be further more development, widely competitive in all situations and all regions.

II. METHODOLOGY

This research intends to analyze the marketing strategies of Thai Halal products which related to the way of life for Thai Muslims. The expected benefit is the marketing strategy for

brand building process for Halal products in Thailand. 4 elements of marketing strategies which necessary for the brand identity creation is the research framework: consists of Attributes, Benefits, Values and Personality; as on Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Represents the Research Framework

The research methodology was applied using qualitative and quantitative; 19 marketing experts with dynamic roles in Thai consumer products were interviewed. In addition, a field survey of 122 Thai Muslims selected from 175 Muslim communities in Bangkok was studied. The sampling group consists of 9 groups of Thai Muslim consumers. But do not specific for quantities of each sampling group. These are two lines of data were used to provide quantitative data.

The questionnaire consists of 4 principle parts of marketing strategy. Each part consists of 15 marketing keywords as following: 1) Benefit; beneficial nutrients product, no toxic or chemical residues, fresh and clean materials, standard of manufacturing, look of product, color, smell, taste, manufacturer's credit. 2) Attribute; standard proof mark, food and drug secure proof mark, Halal products mark, packaging and its materials, attractive graphic, images of product, material, ingredients, description of product, brand name, logo, trademark. 3) Value; healthy products, quality of life, product of expertise, manufacturing of research result, consumers are important, sincere, honest, reliable to all, trusty manufacturer, healthy products. 4) Personality; health care persons, rational person, moral person, justice person, thoughtful person, progressive thinking, active person, sport look, urbanism look, multicultural celebrity, modernism look, news additive person, social activist.

Data analysis will be according to 5 categories of Thai Halal product: 1) Meat 2) Vegetable and Fruits 3) Instant foods and Garnishing ingredient 4) Beverages, Desserts and Snacks 5) Daily hygienic Products; such as soap, shampoo and body lotion.

The values measurement using Rating Scale with Rensis Likert: Likert Scale and the respondent's criteria with 5 levels score answers. The obtained scores within the interval levels

are 0.80 as follows.

- 4.21 to 5.00 is very high agreement.
- 3.41 to 4.20 is high agreement.
- 2.61 to 3.40 is moderate.
- 1.81 to 2.60 is low agreement.
- 1.00 to 1.80 is very low agreement.

The standard values of this research considering to the score of 3.41 or above. The results will be use as a benchmark for branding process and to setting marketing strategies for Halal products in Thailand.

The statistical analysis: using the software package SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) for Windows Version 17 as follows.

Descriptive statistics: a statistic used to summarize information and personal opinions of the designers included frequency and percentage.

Range of opinions on the concept and way of life in Thailand Muslims: On Halal Print Media, the statistics are mean and the standard deviation.

Inference Statistics: a statistic used to test the hypothesis. Test the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

T – Test: to test the difference between the two groups of variables, including gender.

The variance of the data with F - Test used to compare the difference between the averages of the variable over the two groups, including age, education, and occupation by analyzing the ANOVA (One - Way ANOVA) to analyze the differences of Variable between the groups.

Analyze the difference over two groups by the Multiple Comparisons Test with Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) at the 0.05 significance level.

Compare the difference between the independent variables and the dependent variable by using statistical methods, with a correlation coefficient of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient criteria, the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

Detail of correlation coefficient as follows.

- Less than 0.20 is very low.
- 0.20 to 0.39 is low.
- 0.40 to 0.59 is moderate.
- 0.60 to 0.79 is higher.
- 0.80 And above is very high.

Also, if the correlation coefficient (r) close to 1 or -1 indicates that the two variables are related, and if (r) = 1 or above 1 indicates that the two variables are perfectly correlated.

III. RESULTS

Overall, the findings of this research reveal to 5 categories of Thai Halal product: 1) Meat 2) Vegetable and Fruits 3) Instant foods and Garnishing ingredient 4) Beverages, Desserts and Snacks 5) Hygienic daily products; such as soap, shampoo and body lotion. The analysis of all categories according to 4 elements of marketing strategies of Thai consumer products as are: 1) Benefit 2) Attribute 3) Value 4) Personality. Detail of each category as following:

1) The Category of Meat

The marketing strategies of Thai Halal products according to the category of Meat as are: 1) Benefit; the characteristics of the product with its benefit. Consumers will purchase this product with the reason of; it is beneficial nutrients product, there are no toxic or chemical residues, fresh and clean materials 2) Attribute; the exterior images that attract to consumer. Consumers will purchase this product with the reason of; there is a standard proof mark, food and drug secure proof mark and Halal products mark. Packaging and its materials should be draw attention. Use an attractive graphic. Use outstanding images of product, material or ingredients. 3) Value; the value of products that affect to consumers perception; it is healthy products. Accumulate quality of life. It is a product of expertise, manufacturing of research result. Consumers are important. It's sincere, honest and reliable to all. 4) Personality; reflection of consumers thought. The Personality feedback to them after they were consumes this product; they are health care persons. They are the rational person, moral person, justice person and thoughtful person like a progressive thinking; as on Fig. 2.

Criteria consider ≥ 3.41

Fig. 2 Represents the Category of Meat

2) The Category of Vegetable and Fruits

The marketing strategies of Thai Halal products according to the category of Vegetable and Fruits as are: 1) Benefit; the characteristics of the product with its benefit. Consumers will purchase this product with the reason of; there are no toxic or chemical residues, fresh and clean materials, it is beneficial nutrients product, standard of manufacturing. Look of product and its taste. 2) Attribute; the exterior images that attract to consumer. Consumers will purchase this product with the

reason of; Use outstanding images of product, material or ingredients. There are description of product and ingredients. There are marks of standard proof, mark of food and drug secure proof and Halal products mark. Packaging and its materials should be draw attention. Use an attractive graphic and color. 3) Value; the value of products that affect to consumers perception; it is the products of trusty manufacturer, healthy products. Accumulate quality of life. It is a product of expertise, manufacturing of research result. Consumers are important. It's sincere, honest and friendly to all. 4) Personality; reflection of consumers thought. The Personality feedback to them after they were consumes this product; they are health care persons. They are the rational person, moral person, justice person. Active person and sport look, thoughtful person like a progressive thinking; as on Fig. 3.

Criteria consider ≥ 3.41

Fig. 3 Represents the Category of Vegetable and Fruits

3) The Category of Instant Foods and Garnishing Ingredient

The marketing strategies of Thai Halal products according to the category of Instant foods and garnishing ingredient as are: 1) Benefit; the characteristics of the product with its benefit. Consumers will purchase this product with the reason of; fresh and clean materials, there are no toxic or chemical residues, it is beneficial nutrients product, standard of manufacturing and manufacturer's credit. 2) Attribute; the exterior images that attract to consumer. Consumers will purchase this product with the reason of; Use outstanding images of product, material or ingredients. There are description of product and ingredients. There are marks of standard proof, mark of food and drug secure proof and Halal products mark. Packaging and its materials should be draw attention. Use an attractive graphic and color. There is a brand

name, logo or trademark. 3) Value; the value of products that affect to consumers perception; it is an up to date product, a product of expertise, healthy products. It is the products of trusty manufacturer, great origin and classic legend. 4) Personality; reflection of consumers thought. The Personality feedback to them after they were consumes this product; urbanism look and multicultural celebrity. They are health care persons. Modernism look, active look and news additive person, thoughtful person like a progressive thinking and social activist; as on Fig. 4.

Criteria consider ≥ 3.41

Fig. 4 Represents the Category of Instant Foods, and Garnishing Ingredient

4) The Category of Beverages, Desserts and Snacks

The marketing strategies of Thai Halal products according to the category of Beverages, Desserts and Snacks as are: 1) Benefit; the characteristics of the product with its benefit. Consumers will purchase this product with the reason of; fresh and clean materials, it is beneficial nutrients product. There are good taste, great smell and natural color. There are no toxic or chemical residues, standard of manufacturing and manufacturer's credit. 2) Attribute; the exterior images that attract to consumer. Consumers will purchase this product with the reason of; Use outstanding images of product, material or ingredients. There are marks of standard proof, mark of food and drug secure proof and Halal products mark.

Packaging and its materials should be draw attention. Use an attractive graphic and color. There is a brand name, logo or trademark. There are description of product and ingredients. 3) Value; the value of products that affect to consumers perception; it is an up to date product, healthy products. It is the products of trusty manufacturer, a product of expertise, environment friendly. 4) Personality; reflection of consumers thought. The Personality feedback to them after they were consumes this product; generation of digital edge. Modernism look, active, funny and joyful person, urbanism look and multicultural celebrity. Sport man, progressive thinking person; as on Fig. 5.

Criteria consider ≥ 3.41

Fig. 5 Represents the Category of Beverages, Desserts and Snacks

5) The Category of Hygienic Daily Products

The marketing strategies of Thai Halal products according to the category of Hygienic daily products as are: 1) Benefit; the characteristics of the product with its benefit. Consumers will purchase this product with the reason of; reputation of the manufacturer. Fresh and clean materials, there are no toxic or chemical residues. Look of product, standard of manufacturing and manufacturer's credit, reputation of the origin. 2) Attribute; the exterior images that attract to consumer. Consumers will purchase this product with the reason of; there is a standard proof mark, food and drug secure proof mark and Halal products mark. Good looking packaging. Packaging and

its materials should be draw attention. Use an attractive graphic. There are brand name, logo and trademark. There are description of product and ingredients. Use outstanding images of product, material or ingredients. 3) Value; the value of products that affect to consumers perception; it is a product of expertise, friendly for all. It is the products of trusty manufacturer. Consumer always comes first as priority service. It is healthy products that accumulate quality of life. Manufacture of research. It is an up to date products. 4) Personality; reflection of consumers thought. The Personality feedback to them after they were consumes this product; they are health care persons. Modernism look, sport look, progressive thinking, active look and news additive person, thoughtful person like a progressive thinking and social activist, urbanism look and multicultural celebrity, funny look and joyful look; as on Fig. 6.

Criteria consider ≥ 3.41

Fig. 6 Represents the Category of Hygienic Daily Products

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The marketing strategies of Thai Halal products according to the category of Meat should be focus on the beneficial nutrients, without chemical residues, fresh and clean materials. Wrap with standard proof mark, food and drug secure proof mark and Halal products mark. Draw attention with attractive graphic, images and packaging. Identify to healthy products, quality of life, product of expertise, manufacturing of research result. As a health care persons, rational person, moral person,

justice person, thoughtful person, progressive thinking

The marketing strategies of Thai Halal products according to the category of Vegetable and Fruits should be focus on safety, fresh, clean, nutrients and taste. Wrap with outstanding images, products description, standard proof mark, food and drug secure proof mark and Halal products mark. Draw attention with attractive graphic and color. Identify to the trusty manufacturer, healthy products, quality of life, and product of expertise. As a health care persons, rational person, moral person, justice person, active person and sport look.

The marketing strategies of Thai Halal products according to the category of Instant foods and garnishing ingredient should be focus on fresh and clean, without chemical residues, nutrients, standard of manufacturing and their credit. Wrap with outstanding images, description, standard proof mark, food and drug secure proof mark and Halal products mark. Draw attention with attractive packaging, graphic and color, brand name, logo and trademark. Identify to an up to date product, product of expertise, healthy products, trusty manufacturer, great origin and classic legend. Reflex to an urban look, celebrity, health care persons, modernism look, active look, news additive person and social activist.

The marketing strategies of Thai Halal products according to the category of Beverages, Desserts and Snacks should be focus on fresh, clean, nutrients, good taste, great smell and natural color, without chemical residues and manufacturer's credit. Wrap with outstanding images, standard proof mark, food and drug secure proof mark and Halal products mark. Draw attention with attractive packaging, graphic and color, brand name, logo and trademark. Identify to an up to date product, healthy products, trusty manufacturer, product of expertise, environment friendly. Reflex to the generation of digital edge, modernism, active, funny, joyful, urban, celebrity and sport look.

The marketing strategies of Thai Halal products according to the category of Hygienic daily products should be focus on manufacturer's credit, fresh, clean, without chemical residues, origin and legend. Wrap with the standard proof mark, food and drug secure proof mark and Halal products mark. Draw attention with attractive packaging, graphic and color, brand name, logo and trademark, product description. Identify to a product of expertise, friendly, trusty, consumer and service, quality of life, up to date products. Reflex to health care persons, modernism look, sport look, progressive thinking, active look, news additive person, thoughtful person, progressive thinking, social activist, urbanism look and multicultural celebrity, funny look and joyful look.

These are 4 principle parts of marketing strategy with the same direction to Philip Kotler; who has written "Principles of Marketing" [7] in the year of 2012. The research results will be use for building the brand of Thai Halal products with 4 steps of branding device calls 4-D Branding [8]; the marketing strategy of Creative Juice \ G 1 co., ltd. as are: 1) Discovery; the story of brand that found from consumer and marketing analysis 2) Disruption; the differentiate to the brand with different brand idea 3) Disparity; the distribution of brand idea to consumer with communications media and design process

as are: logo, label, packaging, advertising, printing media, outdoor media, corporate identity system, some suitable graphic design on packaging representation; as on Fig. 7. The next steps in this research will be a closer examination of an attribute; the exterior images that attract to consumer. 4) Determine; the measurement and evaluation of the appealable of brand idea to consumer.

Fig. 7 Represents Graphic Design on Packaging

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